

**NEW PROPOSALS FOR TRANSFORMABLE ARCHITECTURE,
ENGINEERING AND DESIGN**
In the honor of Emilio Pérez Piñero

Félix Escrig & José Sánchez (Eds)

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www.starbooks.es

NEW PROPOSALS FOR TRANSFORMABLE ARCHITECTURE,
ENGINEERING AND DESIGN
PRIMERA EDICIÓN. 2013.

Imprime: PRINCOLOR.es
ISBN: 978-84-939565-3-0
Depósito Legal: SE-1666-2013

Portada: Fotografía nocturna Cubierta Piscina Olimpica San Pablo. Sevilla. Escrig & Sánchez.

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Proceedings of the First Conference Transformables 2013.
In the Honor of Emilio Perez Piñero
18th-20th September 2013,
School of Architecture Seville, Spain
EDITORIAL STARBOOKS. Felix Escrig and Jose Sanchez (eds.)

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Origami Folding Patterns in the work of F. Ll. Wright.

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Summary: This article traces a series of road marks that denote common roots in the works of F. Ll. Wright, related in his inspiration of the use of triangular base geometries and some concepts near to projective strategies inspired by a playful knowledge of paperwork, acquired by using F. Fröebel “gifts”, and structural and space mechanisms of Origami folding patterns.

In the images accompanying this article, we see significant architectonic elements and furniture, designed by Wright based on the principles of plates, facets, and folds, that could help him to generate dynamic spaces, rich in nuances and rhythms. Luminaires made in copper are perhaps the most direct examples of the application of the principles of the art of Origami and Kirigami (art that combines the fold of paper with the cut), into a single material, which is subjected to the action of bending to confer a more rigid and visually attractive form, which is able to present individually or in a group, forming more complex and with high value abstract and geometric spatial configurations. F. Ll. Wright was able to masterfully use these folding geometries, developing them not only in small scale in these luminaires but also in medium-scale in the furniture and interiors, and large scale in many of his buildings.

With the folded covers of the ascending passage until the Guest House of the Edgar J. Kaufmann House, Wright not only proposes a new way of thinking and using the concrete as a folded plate, but also traces a structural solution that surpasses the limits, and opens significant new architectonic variables. This reinforced concrete laminar structure, with its folded surface geometry and bowed in the plant, achieves surprising and almost magical stability and rigidity, as if a simple and slight gesture of folded paper is involved. Supported by minimum metal columns, represents all the conceptual and structural achievements of the fold. With this simple gesture of folding, Wright gives a fluid continuity to the two proposed programs. As a youth entertainment, runs a folded ribbon that masterfully connects the Guest House with the main house.

The work of F. Ll. Wright emerges here to inspire new spatial geometries and complex folded morphologies that enable multiple and heterogeneous applications on architecture, and offers to us a global vision and, at the same time, a focal point, a thread of narrative intensity and creative potential.

Keywords: *origami tessellations, folding patterns, folded plate systems, design methodology.*

FRÖEBEL AND THE FIRST SPATIAL NOTIONS.

From the abstraction of natural forms towards the creation of a new universe of complex geometries.

It seems a dare to write about Frank Lloyd Wright without falling into highly repeated clichés. It is not the intention of this article to delve into his work or life. But rather to trace a series of road marks, that denote some intrinsic ideas which seems to share a common root in its inspiration by the use of triangular base geometries and some concepts near to projective strategies inspired by a playful knowledge of paper work and structural and space mechanisms of folded morphologies.

Known is that F. Ll. Wright’s mother Anna Lloyd Jones was a very active county school teacher interested in developing better educational strategies. During a visit to an exhibition in Philadelphia in 1876, Anna saw a series of educational works created by Friedrich Wilhelm August Fröebel, thanks to this she discovered and became interested about the new teaching methodologies from

Friedrich Fröebel that were been implemented in pre-school education during the nineteenth century.

Fig. 01 Froebel games in the play room of Home & Studio of F. Ll. W. Photography: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-15). “Maple blocks... have been in my fingers until today”, said Frank Lloyd Wright in his autobiography, referring to the influence of Fröebel blocks in his work.

Anna Lloyd Jones decided to apply these advanced educational methodologies in her son by giving to him the series of Fröbel games. This relation has been deeply studied by Jeanne Spielman [1] in the book "Intimate Triangle: Architecture of Crystals, Frank Lloyd Wright and the Fröbel Kindergarten" where Jeanne exposes the thesis that there is a deep connection between the discoverer of crystal symmetry Professor Christian Samuel Weiss (1780-1856), his "student" F. Froebel and the works of F. Ll. Wright.

The educative series of Fröbel where a range of "blocks" and boxes of wood with surprises and presents that as Juan Bordes Caballero [2] explains were structured in "Gifts" and "Occupations", in which apart from well known "box of blocks" that brings "gifts of architecture", also were the tessellation with flat pieces of wood, the braided with strips of paper, the folding (7th occupation), the collage...

Fig. 02 (left) Divided Square Puzzle -Die Kunst zu Parquetieren-. From the seventh gift: tessellation of the plane. (right) Fröbel Album with models for the seventh occupation "the fold". Source: Bordes Caballero, Juan. "La infancia de las vanguardias". Cátedra Ediciones 2007.

Kathleen Thorne-Thomsen [3] outlined in the book "Frank Lloyd Wright for Kids", the deep relationship of Wright with the nature surroundings and its ability to abstract natural objects in flat geometries. K. Thorne-Thomsen intuits that Fröbel games should be a point of support for the awakening of artistic knowledge of Wright, helping him to understand the world and their morphological relations.

Fig. 03 F. LL. W. References Composition (down left) Bradley House Window Wood. Adaptation of a F. Ll.

Wright design for a stained-glass window in Kankakee Illinois in 1900. Source: <http://www.franklloydwright.com/browse.cfm/4,648.html> (rest) detail p. 68-71 of "Frank Lloyd Wright for Kids". Kathleen Thorne-Thomsen.

Thorne-Thomsen suggests by these exercises, that the natural evolution of learning with Fröbel games continues in Wright through the exploration of geometric and abstract possibilities for origami.

2. ORIENTAL INSPIRATION.

At the end of the 19th century and early 20th century an interest for the cultural expressions of the "exotic" countries was widespread into European and North American societies. Thanks to the universal exhibitions many non-Western cultures were able to show and export their manufactured products with great success to the society of industrialized countries.

Japanese culture was not stranger to these new open airs of commercial and cultural communication. Along the first universal exhibitions of mid-19th century Japan opened itself to the West, ending several centuries of isolationism.

It was, in these exhibitions, where Japan showed the best of his art, prints, engravings, ink drawings, fabrics and probably the first origami books... which accounted for the Western countries a fresh air that renewed their artistic concepts, discovering new sensitivities and creative worlds.

Between architects and artists of the time arouse a passion that took root in their future creations, in fact was the famous historicist architect of Chicago Joseph Lyman Silsbee, the first architect that Wright worked for, that became the teacher who showed to Wright the delights of oriental art.

A red Japanese square stamp highlights in the extensive library of Wright, is the tool that Wright used to mark in property his books and drawings. It is not a coincidence that he used this type of design, in fact since he discovered the Japanese prints, he was impressed and amazed by this kind of art.

Thanks to the work of Margaret Klinkow and the F. Ll. W. Home & Studio Foundation [4] we can learn about many of the books that compose the Wright collection. Among them we can stand out here three of those referred to the Art and Eastern cultures:

- Conder, Josiah, F.R.I.B.A. The floral Art of Japan. Yokohama, Shanghai, Hong Kong and Singapore: Kelly and Walsh, Ltd., 1899. 142 p.
- Pushman, Garabed T. Art Panels from the Handlooms of the Far Orient as Seen by a Native Rug Weaver Garabed T. Pushman..Chicago : R. R. Donnelly & Sons Co., 1902. 79 p.
- Strange, Edward F. Japanese Illustration: A History of the Arts of Wood-Cutting and Colour Printing in Japan. London: George Bell and Sons, 1904. 155 p.

Besides two books performed by Wright:

- Wright, Frank Lloyd. Scrapbook of 55 photographs taken or acquired by Frank Lloyd Wright in Japan. 1905.
- Wright, Frank Lloyd. The Japanese Print: An Interpretation. Chicago: The Ralph Fletcher Seymour Co., Fine Arts Building, 1912. 35 p.

Fig. 04. Interior of the "Library". F. Ll. Wright. Home & Studio (1939-1944). 951 Chicago Avenue, Oak Park, Chicago. Author: Frank Lloyd Wright. Photos: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-15) According to the restorers of the Home & Studio and the related book "Building a Legacy", the objects that are shown are the originals which are exposed following the guidelines set by the descendants of Wright and known photographic records.

Among the rooms of the F. Ll. Wright Home & Studio is remarkable Wright's private studio called "The Library", the private room where he used to present the final plans to his clients. The following photographs, taken after the last restoration, show multiple Japanese prints, lithographs and objects.

According to Julia Meech [5], associate curator of Japanese art at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, Wright was not only a collector but an intense and passionate dealer in Japanese art, so much so that for a long period of his life his main income was thanks to trade with Japanese woodblock prints.

In the background of the photography of the "Library" we can recognize a small bundle of cloth with blue stampings that wrapped two ceramic pots, finishing in a delicate knot at the top (see image above, right top). Located in the most important room professionally for Wright, this small object is derived from the ancient religious offerings that are the origin of the art of origami [6], possibly bought by the Wrights on one of their trips to Japan.

DESIGNING WITH TRIANGULAR BASE GEOMETRIES AND FOLDED SURFACES.

Fig. 05 Hall "Sun Trap" of the house of Wright's daughter. Detail of photograph appeared on page 60 of the book "Frank Lloyd Wright, 1867-1959. Building for democracy". [7]

Fig. 06 F. LL. Wright wooden seats selection. (Left) Kentuck Knob Armchair home (right) side Chair for Gregor Affleck House (1940-1941, Bloomfield Hills, Michigan). Cypress plywood. Milwaukee Art Museum. Source: "Taliesin 100 years 1911-2011". Quarterly Winter 2011 / Vol. 22. No. 1 Commemorative Issue. Frank Lloyd Wright Foundation.

In the photographs accompanying these lines we see significant architectonic elements and furniture, designed by Wright based on the principles of plates, facets and folds, that could help him to generate dynamic spaces, rich in nuances and rhythms.

As we can read in the magazine Quarterly vol.22, [8] Wright once commented that when he went into a cabinet shop that made furniture with curlicues and elaborate cutting and splicing, he saw half the forests of the nation lying on the floors as sawdust and wood shavings. To avoid this needless waste, his designs for the use of wood, including interior trim as well as furniture, were produced in straight lines, simple and geometric, in order to most conservatively make use of the materials.

Fig. 07. Outdoor luminaires. The Kentuck Knob House. 1953. 723 Kentuck Road, Chalk Hill (PA) author: Frank Lloyd Wright. Photography: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-19)

Fig. 08. Geometric construction of the Outdoor Luminaire for Knob House. Pablo De Souza.

Fig. 09. Ceiling lights. Outside of the offices of the Johnson Wax. (1939-1944). 1525 Howe Street, Racine (WI) author: Frank Lloyd Wright. Photography: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-15)

Luminaires made in copper are perhaps the most direct example of application of the principles of the art of Origami and Kirigami (art that combines the fold of paper with the cut), into a single material, in this case metal, which is subjected to the action of bending to confer a more rigid and visually attractive form, which is able to present individually or in a group, forming more complex and with high value abstract and geometric spatial configurations. F. Ll. Wright was able to masterfully use these geometries, developing them not only in small scale in these luminaires but also in medium scale in the furniture and interiors, and large scale in many of his buildings.

There are many cases in which the covers of the buildings of Wright become wings to the wind, they emerge in such a way, moving away of the basement, become tilted and folded, highlighted with continuous lines and textured facets... even seem to want to raise and fly.

Wright explores hexagonal based plants in several projects, searching of a more flexible plant that offers rich and free indoor spaces. This is the case of the Honeycomb House, which through angles of 120° generates multiple spatial variations and open views to its surroundings.

The ascending passage until the Guest House of the Edgar J. Kaufmann House often go unnoticed for many editions of the works of F. Ll. Wright. The limited space to show the most important part of his works and the extensive and sublime Wright production, causes that most of the dedicated monographs obviate or cannot fully reproduce many of his architectural proposals.

Fig. 10 Edgar J. Kaufmann House. (Fallingwater, 1939) 1491 Mill Run Rd., Mill Run (PA -Pennsylvania). author: Frank Lloyd Wright. Photography: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-19)

As we can see on the covers of the ascending passage, this reinforced concrete laminar structure, with its folded surface geometry and bowed in plant, achieves a surprising and almost magical stability and rigidity, as if a simple and slight gesture of folded paper is involved. Supported by minimum metal columns, represents all the conceptual and structural achievements of the fold.

Fig. 11 Covers of the ascending passage towards the Guest House of the Edgar J. Kaufmann House (Fallingwater, 1939) 1491 Mill Run Rd., Mill Run (PA - Pennsylvania). Author: Frank Lloyd Wright. Photography: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-19)

With this simple gesture of folding, Wright gives a fluid continuity to the two proposed programmes. As a youth entertainment, runs a folded ribbon that masterfully connects the Guest House with the main house.

It becomes so the subtle counterpoint to the overall composition of horizontal planes contrasted by the two large vertical stone volumes of the set.

Fig. 12 Geometric Construction of the covers of the ascending passage towards the Guest House of the Edgar J. Kaufmann House (Fallingwater, 1939) Pablo De Souza.

With these folded covers, Wright not only proposes a new way of thinking and using the concrete as a folded plate, but also traces a structural solution that surpasses the limits, and opens significant new architectonic variables. Even before the emerge of the international movement of concrete laminar folded structures that, according to Rafael García [9], had its heyday during the 50s and the 60s certifying their symbolic end at the Congress about folded plates that held the International Association of Shell Structures in 1970, coincided its progressive abandonment by the increase of the labour cost, and the changing aesthetics trends.

F. Ll. Wright liked to experiment with basic formal configurations resulting from the twinning of primary volumes, pyramidal, prismatic... Through the differentiation of the different facets of the volumes with geometric textures and finishes materials, enhanced the presence of corners and protrusions, which added bumps that accentuated vectors of directions and pointed edges... This series of creative strategies links directly to the games of Fröebel.

Fig. 13 Sculpture and Vase at the F. Ll. Wright. Home & Studio (1939-1944). 951 Chicago Avenue, Oak Park,

Chicago. Author: Frank Lloyd Wright. Photography: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-15)

It is pertinent here to reconsider the relationship between the prismatic and crystallographic morphologies. We can consider that something is or has been folded when it comes from another source untransformed.

Understanding that prismatic faceted forms can be made by folding thin films, it is clear that these generally polyhedral shapes were developed on paper during the school period, and are much more representative of the work of the architect who thinks on spaces compared to solid crystalline forms that are generally convex, free of gaps of significant internal voids, which are formed by polishing procedures and “diamond cuttings”.

Thus, the folded sheet and its architectural and constructive potential, become not only an outward expression of the form but also a delimitator of the interior space.

Collected in the book “Frank Lloyd Wright's Sacred Architecture” by Anat Geva [10], a good number of religious buildings shows these morphological characteristics and projective strategies. The Beth Sholom Synagogue is a good example of these personal explorations, its formal proximity to the triangulations generated by Origami techniques is a reflection of the interest of Wright to develop this type of morphological and perhaps conceptual proposals.

Fig. 14 Beth Sholom Synagogue. (1959) 8231 Old York Rd, Elkins Park, Philadelphia (Pa). Author: Frank Lloyd Wright. Photography: Pablo De Souza (2011-04-20)

Thanks to its innovative glass roof and its structural lightness, the Beth Sholom Synagogue has become a jewel of light, a milestone on the horizon, an entity with high religious and mythical power.

Although it is currently in poor condition with rust-stained glasses, still you can see the magical space that is generated in its interior. The different planes that overlook seem to levitate, floating over our heads, they generate a mystical and relaxing space, as if in clouds we were, in the words of Wright: “when a man comes into a

place of worship, should feel as resting on the large hands of God”.

CONCLUSIONS

As Juan Bordes writes in “La infancia de las vanguardias” (Avant-gardes Childhood) this is not a closed story, it wants to generate many questions and open avenues for possible research and applications in future design and architecture, it aims to rescue, however briefly, the childish scenery lived by one of the most important architects, dusting off his old school books and toys. This research seeks to recover one of the influences, the teachings and the creative inspirations that modified, and continue to make new visions and creations, in the world of art and architecture.

But perhaps the reader thinks that this is a naive story, that summarize the creative intentions of great masters such as F. Ll. Wright in a series of works apparently inspired by origami or paper folding is as little biased and uncertain. Nothing is further from reality, with this research I want to highlight more forcefully the kaleidoscopic world of architectural creation, rescuing from oblivion the conceptual and morphological, contributions given in the world of architecture through the development and expansion of geometric knowledge of the fold.

In the current contemporary context of creation and thanks to the influence of the new artistic languages and means of creation, the architectural project may be ephemeral, ethereal and audiovisual, a temporary urban installation, and no longer exclusively eternal heavy and immobile. Courses like Folding Architecture [11] taught by Sophia Vyzoviti and Pablo De Souza partakes in this new phase of hybridization and crossbreeding inherent to contemporary creative trends, in which traditional art of Origami has served and still serves as creative inspiration enhances its maximum expressiveness as a medium and as a catalyst for research.

The work of F. Ll. Wright emerges here to inspire new spatial geometries and complex morphologies that enable multiple and heterogeneous applications on architecture, and offers to us a global vision and at the same time a focal point, a thread of narrative intensity and creative potential.

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ISBN:978-84-939565-3-0

9 788493 956530

